

1500 cm^{-1} (benzene ring). The UV spectrum of the compound B in ethanol shows absorption maxima at 247, 257, and 322 nm which is very similar to that of citropten³. That compound B contains an epoxide ring is evident from the fact that it gave a diol (II). $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$, m.p. 124°, on treatment with aqueous oxalic acid (1%). The diol consumed one mole of periodic acid. The IR spectrum of the diol in Nujol mull shows bands at 3510 cm^{-1} and 3400 cm^{-1} (glycolic OH groups), 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl), 1610 cm^{-1} and 1500 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring). The

(I)

(II)

NMR spectrum of the diol (CDCl_3 , 60MHz) shows a pair of doublets centered at 6.22 δ (1H, *d*, $J = 9.5\text{Hz}$) and 7.62 δ (1H, *d*, $J = 9.5\text{Hz}$) for the 3-H and 4-H respectively. The two aromatic protons namely 5-H and 6-H appear as another pair of doublets centered at 6.85 δ (1H, *d*, $J = 8.5\text{Hz}$) and 7.34 δ (1H, *d*, $J = 8.5\text{Hz}$), one of the peaks of the latter overlaps with that of CHCl_3 . The three protons of the methoxy group ($-\text{OCH}_3$) and the six protons of the two methyl groups attached to one of the carbinol carbon atom [$-\text{C}(\text{OH})-(\text{CH}_3)_2$] appear as sharp singlets at 3.93 δ (3H) and 1.31 δ (6H) respectively. The peak at 2.62 δ (2H) which disappears on D_2O treatment is due to the two protons of the alcoholic hydroxyl groups ($-\text{C}-\text{OH}$). The carbinyl proton ($-\text{CHOH}$) appears as a broad multiplet centered at 3.64 δ (1H). The two benzylic protons appear as a typical multiplet centered at 3.03 δ . The above data show that the diol has the structure (II). Direct comparison with an authentic sample has not been possible but there is little doubt that compound B is identical with auropten⁴ (I, Lit. record; m.p. 98°).

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Prof. S. M. Sircar, Director of Bose Institute for his interest in this work. They are also grateful to Drs. A. P. B. Sinha and K. G. Das of National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, India, for the NMR and mass spectra of the compounds. One of us (A. B.) is indebted to C.S.I.R. for financial assistance.

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pH metric study of complexes of some metal ions with salicylaldehyde-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone

Y. N. BHATT, K. K. PATEL, K. J. SHAH, R. S. PATEL*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University
Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 29 March 1975; revised 24 July 1975;
accepted 14 August 1975

LIGANDS such as thiosemicarbazones are studied to a limited extent pH-metrically. Here salicylaldehyde-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (SPT) derivative is studied with metals like VO^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} . The formation constants for their metals were calculated by Calvin and Wilson pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants are determined in 50% aqueous dioxane medium.

Experimental

The ligand salicylaldehyde-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone was synthesized and crystallised to get analytically pure (m.p. 188°)¹. The solution of SPT was prepared in dioxane (BDH, AnalaR grade) which was further purified by standard method of Vogel². Metal nitrates used were of AnalaR grade which were estimated by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods. Phillips pH meter was used for pH measurements. pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions having pH 4.33 and 9.1 at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

All titrations were carried out in a 100 ml beaker kept in water thermostat maintained at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Thirty five to forty five readings were taken in each case. Each titration was repeated to get reproducible results. The metal ligand ratio was maintained 1:5. The titration curves are given in Fig. 1.

Blank titrations: A mixture of 2ml of 0.1M HNO_3 , 5 ml of 1.0M KNO_3 , 25 ml dioxane and 18 ml of water (to make the total of 50 ml in all titrations)

* For Correspondence

was titrated with 0.2M NaOH until the pH rises to about 12.

Fig. 1. Titration curves for SPT systems.

Ligand titrations: A mixture of 2 ml of 0.1M HNO₃, 5 ml of 1.0M KNO₃, 5 ml of 0.01M ligand solution in dioxane, 20 ml of dioxane and 18 ml of water was titrated with 0.2M NaOH solution.

Metal titrations :

A mixture of 2 ml of 0.1M HNO₃+5 ml of 1.0M KNO₃+5 ml of 0.01 ligand+1 ml of 0.01M metal nitrate solution (in case of cobalt 0.5 ml solution was taken)+20 ml of dioxane+17 ml of water was titrated with 0.2M NaOH solution.

Results and Discussions

The practical proton-ligand stability constant for the ligand was calculated with the help of $\bar{n}_A$ values at different B values (pH meter readings in 50% aqueous dioxan-medium). $\bar{n}_A$ is calculated by the method of Irving & Rossotti³ as adopted by Jabalpurwala *et al*⁴. Plot of $\log \bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A$ against B is done to obtain a best straight line. From this straight line the values of the practical stability constant was obtained using the relation

$$\log {}^pK_1^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$$

The proton ligand stability constant obtained is 7.94×10^9 . For metal ligand stability constants $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by the method of Jabal-

purwala *et al*⁴. The values of $\bar{n}$ are plotted against pL . The formation curves are represented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Formation curves for SPT systems.

The values of $\log K_1$ were calculated by half integral method. But for calculation of $\log K_2$ least square method⁵ in which $\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})HL}$ was plotted against $(\bar{n}-2)HL$ and Olerup's method was also used as there was not much difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$.

The average stability constants are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Metal	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Cu ²⁺	10.28	—	—
Co ²⁺	9.84	9.46	19.30
VO ²⁺	9.44	—	—
Ni ²⁺	8.94	—	—

For $\log K_1$, it is observed that stability constants are in the order $Cu^{2+} > Co^{2+} > VO^{2+} > Ni^{2+}$.

Thus, Irving William's rule is not violated except for Ni²⁺ which forms less stable complex.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. A. Thaker, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar, for providing

laboratory facilities; to C.S.I.R., New Delhi and Gujarat State for the award of scholarships to Y.N.B. and K.K.P., respectively.

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A few benzylidene derivatives of N-substituted succinimides

D'COSTA ROSARIO AND V. V. NADKARNY*

Nadkarny Sacasa Research Laboratory,
Chemistry Department,
St. Xavier's College, Bombay-1.

Manuscript received 23 April 1975, revised 28 July 1975,
accepted 12 August 1975.

IN the Perkin's¹ Reaction, aromatic aldehydes condense with acid anhydrides possessing two hydrogen atoms on an α -carbon atom, in the presence of sodium acetate to give β -aryl acrylic acids. The reaction has been modified and condensations have been effected using aldehydes and carboxylic acids possessing α -hydrogen atoms. De Tar² used this procedure in the condensation of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde with phenylacetic acid, with triethylamine as

cinnimides were synthesized according to the method as given in Wild⁵.

The *N*-substituted imides, as obtained above were condensed with benzaldehyde, acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate for 4-5 hr under the conditions of Perkin's reaction to afford compounds of the type II.

All attempts to isolate cinnamic acid were unsuccessful. Earlier, a striking example had been cited where identical conditions were employed⁴.

A probable explanation is afforded as follows: Since the reaction is base-catalysed, the carbonion formed from *N*-substituted succinimide is secondary as compared to the formation of primary carbonion from acetic anhydride. Therefore the secondary carbonion is relatively less stable and more reactive, hence the product.

Similar condensations were effected using anisaldehyde to yield compounds of the type III.

The derivatives gave expected nitrogen analysis.

TABLE. DERIVATIVES OF THE TYPE II* AND III*

Compound	Mol. formula	m.p. °C
IIa	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	125°-6°
IIb	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	160°-1°
IIc	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	170°-1°
IIIa	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	136°
IIIb	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ NCl	165°-6°
IIIc	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	166°-7°

*(All the melting points are taken in a concentrated H₂SO₄ bath and may need further correction).

a = -phenyl. b = -*p*-chlorophenyl, c = -naphthyl

a base. The most significant applications¹ are: condensation of cyclic sulphur compounds such as rhodanine³ (containing active methylene groups) with aromatic aldehydes and the famous Erlenmeyer's azalactone synthesis.

N-Substituted succinimides contain active methylene groups and the aim of the present investigation is the extension of Perkin's reaction to these imides to form benzylidene derivatives. Therefore, *N*-phenyl-, *N*-*p*-chlorophenyl-, and *N*-naphthyl- suc-

Experimental procedure

A mixture of *N*-substituted succinimide (0.5 g) and aromatic aldehyde (0.6 g), acetic anhydride (2.5 ml) and fused sodium acetate (0.1 g), is refluxed at 170°-190° and maintained at that temperature for 4-5 hr. The reaction flask is then connected to steam distillation apparatus and excess of aldehyde is steam distilled. The resultant mixture, on cooling, affords long needles of the product which on crystallization